

Result of our research and development project is to be founded a unique node solution, which can be used for covering any roof structure with an open surface without any restrictions, eliminating the limitations of the previous design, thus providing a revolutionary solution to the world of architecture. The research aimed at implementing junctions with more than six elements are connected and adjacent joints with an angle of less than 45 degrees, as well as junctions with a solid angle of more than 15 degrees can be considered successful, since the structural behavior of the completed sample meets the preliminary studies and expectations, being completely watertight. The part of the research related to the cross-section identical pipe connection can also be considered successful, as it exceeded our expectations in terms of load-bearing capacity, installation and aesthetics, as well as from an economic point of view. Overall, the domestic and international construction industry has become richer with a cross-section identical pipe connection in a steel structure field, that can be easily assembled and produced under factory conditions, and it is aesthetic as well.